

Due to space limitations, we removed some of the security analysis from the paper. The following is our **additional security analysis**.

1. Breaking Integrity and Confidentiality of components

- (1) **Breach of confidentiality.** Normally, a host OS can access any physical page or modify the memory layouts. SecFortress unmaps HypBox-related memory regions in the kernel master-page-table to prevent host OS from accessing the HypBoxes' memory. However, a compromised host OS may remap the physical memory of hypervisor to its address space, or other processes. Since physical memory is loaded into the CPU cache in a plain-text state and is not isolated in cacheline, it may leak sensitive information once the host OS implements the above attacks. However, these attacks can be defeated by SecFortress. SecFortress sets the kernel master page-table-pages to be write-protected, and forces the attribute certification prior to memory mapping updates. For the page tables of other processes, since all processes' page tables depend on the kernel master-page-table to add new mappings, SecFortress can limit them as long as it controls the master-page-table. Similarly, a compromised HypBox also cannot access others sensitive information because it has no permission to modify its memory view.
- (2) **Violation of integrity.** A compromised host OS can violate the integrity of the HypBox by directly tampering with the memory. SecFortress defends against such attacks by controlling memory mapping updates and memory access permissions. This means that a compromised host OS doesn't have permission to modify the physical pages that have been assigned to HypBoxes. However, during HypBox creation, a compromised host OS may write malicious code or data to a specific physical page, which will be assigned to the HypBox. SecFortress protects this attack by zeroing out the physical pages before assignment.

2. Hacking the mediator

- (1) **Tampering with SecFortress Code.** During the system boot phase, the attacker may modify the code of SecFortress. We use secure boot to ensure the integrity of mediator. After that, the mediator measures the integrity of the system's code and set all code to be write-protected. In addition, the mediator prohibits mapping new executable memory to outerOS or HypBox, so it can defend code injection attacks.
- (2) **Bypass the protection.** The protection mechanism can be bypassed through executing sensitive instructions shown in Table II. SecFortress dynamically checks and unmaps these instructions in non-TCB components. For new instruction injection attacks, SecFortress defends against them by write-protection. For ROP-based attacks, SecFortress checks the result before a bad consequence occurs. In addition, a binary scanner is used to ensure that there are no such instructions (reuse for ROP gadget) in unexpected code regions. So there is no way to bypass the protection mechanism.
- (3) **DMA attack.** An attacker may access sensitive memory by leveraging DMA. SecFortress defends against such attacks by controlling IOMMU, which is used for DMA I/O address translation. The mediator controls the mapping updates and information in IOMMU, and strictly limits the scope that each guest VM can access.
